

Requirements and Recommendations for Data and Metadata Described and Shared through DORIS

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Abstract

This document sets out the requirements and recommendations that apply to research data shared through DORIS. It is updated continuously as SND develops and in response to feedback on what may be missing or requires clarification.

Swedish National Data Service (SND) is a national research infrastructure that provides services to make research data findable, accessible, and reusable. **DORIS** is SND's tool for describing and sharing data so that they become findable and accessible through the national research data portal **Researchdata.se**. SND's objective is that data and metadata that are described and shared through DORIS should be well documented and comply with the FAIR principles to the greatest extent possible.

In this document, we outline the requirements and recommendations for data and metadata that are described and shared through DORIS, as well as the legal and technical requirements for using DORIS. It is intended for organizations that use SND's repository for data storage (**SND CARE**) and organizations that provide local storage connected to SND's services.

Introduction and purpose

Swedish National Data Service (SND) is a national research infrastructure that provides services to make research data findable, accessible, and reusable. **DORIS** is SND's tool for describing and sharing data so that they become findable and accessible through SND's national research data portal **Researchdata.se**.

This document sets out the requirements and recommendations that apply to data and metadata described and shared through DORIS. It also outlines the legal and technical requirements for using DORIS. An understanding of SND's systems and tools is necessary to fully benefit from the information provided here. For further information about SND, see *Description of SND*.¹

In this document, *sharing data* means making data findable and reusable, either openly (data are available by direct download) or with restricted access (data must be requested).

SND's objective is that the data and metadata that are described and shared through DORIS should be well documented and comply with the FAIR principles² to the greatest extent possible, based on what is applicable for each dataset. The requirements and recommendations in this document are based on this objective, as well as on the need to meet requirements from key stakeholders and partners, such as DataCite's³ requirements for the management of DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers).

Data and metadata described and shared through DORIS must undergo a review process before publication to ensure that the requirements and recommendations are met. Datasets shared using the simplified profile, **Simplified registration**, are subject to specific requirements regarding documentation and review; see the dedicated section below. The review is usually carried out by local research data support staff together with the SND Office. In the future, the aim is for SND to provide support only as needed, and for the data-holding organization responsible for the data (sometimes referred to as the research principal, *forskningshuvudmannen*)⁴ to review and publish datasets independently.

Additional information is available on the SND website, [SND.se](https://snd.se), including practical guidance on handling and checking data and metadata to support the review process conducted by the data-holding organization.

This document is intended for:

- organizations in the SND Network with their own storage solutions (repositories) connected to DORIS;

¹ *Description of SND (Beskrivning av SND)* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6346149>

² Read more about FAIR on [Researchdata.se](https://researchdata.se), [FORCE 11](https://force11.org), or the [Swedish Research Council](https://www.sri.org.uk).

³ <https://datacite.org/>

⁴ The research principal (*forskningshuvudmannen*) is the authority, natural, or legal person in the context of whose operations the research is conducted, and which has the ultimate responsibility for the research. This is typically the HEI or research organization where the researcher was employed when the research was conducted.

- users of SND CARE (SND's repository; see below).

Organizations that have their own storage solutions for research data connected to SND's systems are responsible for the data and metadata their users share through DORIS. Internal reviews must ensure that the data and metadata described and shared comply with the requirements set out in this document.

Organizations that do not have local storage connected to SND's systems use SND CARE for the storage and dissemination of research data. The use of SND CARE is regulated through a service agreement⁵ between SND (University of Gothenburg) and the data-holding organization. SND CARE is a certified repository,⁶ which ensures the quality of the workflows for making research data accessible. Therefore, data share in SND CARE must also comply with the recommendations in this document. The data-holding organization is responsible for the data and ensures that the data are shared correctly and in accordance with applicable legislation (see section on *Legal requirements for sharing data* below). Staff at the SND Office participate in reviewing the documentation level in the data description.

Metadata and documentation

In this document, *metadata and documentation* refer both to the structured information entered into the DORIS form and to the documentation files that describe the data, such as README files, codebooks, variable lists, and technical information.

The requirements apply to metadata for the entire dataset and to information at the file or variable level.

Requirements for metadata and documentation

- The mandatory metadata fields in DORIS must be completed and described as thoroughly as possible, based on the dataset in question. Which metadata fields are mandatory depends on the subject profile selected in DORIS.

The *Description* field is mandatory for all profiles and must be provided in both Swedish and English. The translations do not need to be literal; for longer texts it may be appropriate to refer to the other language version for additional details.

- If there are articles or other publications related to the data, links or complete references to them must be provided. As datasets are typically published before an associated article, it is

⁵ Uppdragsavtal för lagring och förmedling av forskningsdata, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11277529>

⁶ SND CARE holds a CoreTrustSeal certification (<https://www.coretrustseal.org/>).

sufficient to include a provisional reference to the article (including title, author name(s), and year, with “submitted” or “under review” as placeholders for volume, pages, and link or persistent identifier). The metadata must then be updated with a full reference once the article has been published.

- External links must be provided as persistent identifiers (PIDs) when available, such as DOI, Handle, or URN.
- In cases where only metadata are shared through DORIS, because the data are available via another portal or service, the links to the data must be provided as persistent identifiers. As outlined in SND’s PID Policy, *SND Policy for Persistent Identifiers on Datasets*,⁷ resource collections may be exempt from the PID requirement.
- Accompanying documentation⁸ necessary to understand, use, or reproduce the data must be shared alongside the data and metadata. Documentation should include information about how the data were produced, processed, and in what context they were created. What constitutes sufficient documentation depends on factors such as the research field and the type of data. An assessment of whether the documentation is adequate must therefore be made in each individual case.

If data are shared in relation to a specific article or other publication, the requirement for accompanying documentation may be waived. This presupposes that the article or publication in question:

- is openly accessible;
- is linked in the metadata with a persistent identifier (PID);
- contains all information required for the data to be understood and reused, enabling the results to be reproduced independently of additional resources.

Note that a single article is often not sufficient and that supplementary documentation, such as a README file, a variable list, or a codebook, may be required to understand and reuse the material.

Recommendations for metadata and documentation

- Metadata fields that are not mandatory but that are important within the research domain should be described in detail to ensure high quality.

⁷ *SND Policy for Persistent Identifiers on Datasets*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6352451>

⁸ Here, “accompanying information” refers to information that cannot be provided only through standardized metadata fields in the DORIS form.

- Metadata and accompanying documentation should, as far as possible, be understandable to researchers from other disciplines. For highly specialised materials – for example, genetic data or physical experiments – a narrower intended audience may be appropriate.
- The dataset title should describe the contents of the data. If the data are shared in connection with a specific article or other publication, the dataset should not have the same title as the publication. If it is not possible to provide a descriptive title, the recommended title format is: *“Data for: [title of publication]”*.
- Datasets published for a specific analysis, for example for a published article, should be documented as thoroughly as possible to enable replication of the results.
- If a specific article is necessary to understand or reuse the data (see the final bullet point under *Requirements for metadata and documentation*), the article should be preserved to ensure future access. The article does not need to be shared together with the data via DORIS if a persistent identifier or permanent link to the article is provided.
- If only metadata are shared through DORIS, because the data are available via another portal or service, relevant metadata and documentation should be available with the published dataset.

Data

The following section outlines the requirements and recommendations for reviewing data shared through DORIS.

Requirements for data

- The material to be shared and/or described must be research data. In this context, research data refers to digital material from scientific activities or other collected data that can form the basis of a scientific analysis or validate research results, regardless of research domain (thus excluding, for example, presentations, individual graphs, or appendix material).
- Files must be checked for viruses or other malicious code.
- Data must be in formats suitable for sharing. The same data may also be shared in formats suitable for long-term preservation in archives or similar. If the data and/or file formats are highly specific to the research domain and require specialized software to open and use, it may be sufficient for the researcher to confirm the accuracy of the files and indicate which formats are most appropriate.

- If specialized software is required, it must either accompany the data or be described in sufficient detail to enable discovery. The software name and version must be provided, along with any additional information relevant for reuse.
- If code or scripts have been used to process or interpret the data, this must be stated in the data description. Code and/or scripts must be included with or linked to the data files. Information on the programming environment, exact versions of all components used, and any other details relevant for reuse must be provided. Instructions on how to run the scripts must also be included.
- The file package must be complete, meaning that it must contain all information necessary for correct reuse.
- The content of the data files must be checked for personal data or other sensitive information. Further details on reviews relating to personal data and other sensitive information are provided in the *Legal requirements for sharing data* section below.

Recommendations for data

- Files (including folders) should be named in a consistent and comprehensible manner. This is particularly important for large or complex datasets with many files. However, be aware that there may be established standards or best practices for naming and packaging files that may appear unclear to someone unfamiliar with the field. File names, contents, and relationships between files may therefore need to be explained in a supplementary text document.
- Files should be cleaned of irrelevant information, such as formatting that is not significant for the use of the data.
- If data are shared in formats not suitable for long-term preservation, they should, where possible, also be shared in complementary formats.⁹

Simplified registration

DORIS provides the option to describe and share data through a **Simplified registration** profile. This is a metadata profile that contains a minimal set of fields for describing the dataset in question. **SND applies less stringent requirements for the review of data and metadata described and shared through simplified registration.** Consequently, data described and shared in this way comply with the FAIR principles to a lesser extent compared with other dataset descriptions published through DORIS.

⁹ For examples, see [Recommended file formats](#) (SND.se).

Data-holding organizations may choose to introduce additional requirements prior to publication. The SND Office does not conduct any additional review of these dataset descriptions, regardless of where the data are stored.

Requirements for simplified registration

- Data must be shared with an appropriate level of access based on their content. For example, data containing sensitive personal information must be shared with restricted access.
- The material to be shared and/or described must be research data. In this context, research data refers to digital material from scientific activities or other collected data that can form the basis of a scientific analysis or validate research results, regardless of research domain (thus excluding, for example, presentations, individual graphs, or appendix material).

In addition, SND recommends that the metadata provided should be as accurate as possible and that persistent identifiers (such as ORCID for individuals, ROR IDs for organizations, and DOI for linked resources) should be used wherever they exist.

Datasets published through simplified registration may, just like those published via other metadata profiles, later be enriched with more detailed metadata.

Legal requirements for data sharing

In a review of data and metadata, it is important to not only ensure that data and metadata meet high-quality standards in line with the FAIR principles, but to verify that data are managed in accordance with applicable laws, such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the Public Access to Information and Secrecy Act, copyright law, and other relevant legislation. The handling of data in connection with publication must also follow general ethical principles and good research practice.

In DORIS, the researcher (and the local research data support staff involved in the review process) indicates whether the data contain personal data or other protected information and confirms that the dissemination (sharing) of the data complies with applicable legislation.

DORIS provides two levels of access to data:

1. Data are openly accessible and can be downloaded directly;
2. Access to data is restricted, which means that a request to access the data must be assessed by the data-holding organization before the data may be released.

It is the responsibility of each data-holding organization, as they hold the utmost responsibility for the data, to choose the appropriate data access level based on the content of the research data. This is usually done by the researcher responsible for the dataset together with the local research data

support, although procedures may vary between organizations. SND advocates sharing data according to the principle “*as open as possible, but as restricted as necessary*”¹⁰ and recommends taking a precautionary approach in cases of uncertainty; that is, data should not be openly shared if there is any doubt about whether open access is compliant with applicable laws and regulations.

Each data-holding organization must ensure that clear procedures and adequate knowledge are in place to ensure that data sharing is carried out in accordance with mandatory legislation.

Research data must never be disseminated if doing so would constitute an offence under national or international law, such as defamation, breach of confidentiality, dissemination of child sexual abuse material, or other criminal acts. Other issues that must be considered include that data sharing may not take place if it constitutes a copyright infringement or contradict contractual obligations (for example, if agreements with an external third party include specific provisions on rights or confidentiality). To ensure that DORIS is used in compliance with legislation, data-sharing procedures must include controls, and researchers and support staff must have the knowledge required to apply them correctly.

Note that the process for releasing data under restriction (such as a secrecy assessment) is not described here. This assessment must always be carried out by the data-holding organization before any data are released.

Requirements for data storage

Data and associated files shared through DORIS must be stored in a controlled and long-term manner. There are currently two options for data storage:

1. Data are stored in SND CARE, SND’s certified repository. SND is responsible for ensuring that the data and associated files are handled correctly. The use of SND CARE is governed by a service agreement, and where data containing personal data are stored, a data processing agreement is also required.
2. Data are stored in an environment controlled by the data-holding organization. Organizations in the SND Network may connect their local storage to SND’s systems, making it possible to share data via DORIS without transferring the files out of the organization’s control.¹¹ While the technical integration between local storage and DORIS is being developed, an interim solution may be used for sensitive data.¹² This means, in brief, that data shared with

¹⁰ The “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” principle appears in, e.g., the [ALLEA Codex](#), section 2.5, and in the European [Open Data Directive](#), recital 28 and article 10.1.

¹¹ *Integration mellan lärosätets egen lagring och SND (DORIS)*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6346297>

¹² *Interimslösning för egen lagring utan integration med DORIS*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6346587>

restricted access are stored and handled by the data-holding organization in a structured manner, even if technical integration with DORIS has not yet been implemented.

SND does not impose any requirements on how an organization's storage environment is structured or maintained; it is up to each organization to develop the storage support that best suits its own operations. Each organization is also responsible for establishing procedures for how research data are stored.